

2. Proportion of true positive and false positive samples using the presence of infected seedlings as criterion (a) and the proportion of false negative and true negative samples using two successive criteria: presence of infected seedlings and presence of *R. solani*-like colonies on ungerminated seeds (b).

Figure 2 shows the proportion of false positives and false negatives from a large series of samples. Criterion is based on the isolation of *R. solani*-like colonies on ungerminated seeds. There were 37.5% false negatives using the first criterion (presence of infected seedlings), while the proportion of false negatives was reduced to 16.0% using the second criterion in sequence (presence of *R. solani*-like fungus colonizing ungerminated seeds).

When the second criterion alone is considered, low contamination of a soil sample leads to very few false positives (1 and 3, respectively, for IRRI and Pila soils). However, this test leads to relatively high false negative cases (28 and 16, respectively, for IRRI and Pila soils). Nevertheless, c^2 values (19.7 for IRRI and 28.7 for Pila) indicate that this test adequately detects colonization of soil samples by *R. solani*. ■

DNA fingerprinting of bacterial blight pathogen directly from infected leaves

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In this study, we shortened the time required to obtain DNA fingerprints by using pathogen DNA prepared directly from cells leached from infected leaves. Leaves of IR24 plants grown in the greenhouse were inoculated (clip method) with six isolates of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* belonging to different lineages, and infected leaves were collected 14 d later. To 'ooze' bacteria from the leaves, 2-cm-long leaf fragments containing the advancing tip of lesions were cut crosswise into 10 small pieces with flame-sterilized scissors, and then soaked in 400 μ L of sterile distilled water for at least 1 h. The leaf pieces were discarded and the cells concentrated by spinning the suspension for 2 min in a microcentrifuge. Most of the water was discarded, leaving about 25 μ L, in which the cells were resuspended. The cells were lysed in 200 μ L of 70% ethanol (final concentration) and then spun for 10 s to pellet the cell debris. The supernatant was transferred to a new tube and spun for 5 min to precipitate DNA. The DNA was air-dried, dissolved in 10 μ L of sterile water and 5 μ L served as template for polymerase chain reaction (PCR). To check the consistency of the fingerprint patterns, purified DNA from the isolates used for inoculation served as positive controls. Standard PCR protocols were followed using JEL1 /JEL2 primers and with the repPCR primers BOX, ERIC, and REP using DNA from bacterial exudates from lesions and using DNA from cultured cells.

Figure 1 compares the fingerprint patterns from the alcohol lysis method to those obtained using DNA prepared by the potassium acetate method. The latter has a smeary background that obscured some bands, apparently from residual chemical contaminants. When intact cells were used directly in the PCR reaction, the results were incon-

1. Comparison of fingerprints obtained using DNA from *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* PX0112 prepared from cultured cells by the potassium acetate method (lanes 1 and 2) and from cells leached from infected leaves by the alcohol lysis method (lanes 3, 4, 5 and 6). Infected leaves were those of IR24 grown in the greenhouse, and the primers JEL1/JEL2 were used to generate the fingerprints.

sistent. Amplification appeared more efficient when DNA was released by lysis with alcohol, and cellular debris and other contaminants were removed prior to amplification.

To assess the general utility of the method, bacteria were also leached

2. Fingerprint patterns obtained from naturally infected leaves of IR24 (lanes 1, 8, 9, and 10) and near-isogenic lines IRBB4 (lanes 2, 3, 11, and 12), IRBB7 (lanes 4, 5, 13, and 14), and IRBB10 (lanes 6, 7, 15, and 16) grown in two hot spots for bacterial blight disease in the Philippines. The molecular markers (M) consist of a 1-kb ladder. The primers JEL1/JEL2 were used in the PCR method.

from naturally infected leaf samples of IR24 and near-isogenic lines (IRBB4, IRBB7, and IRBB10) planted in Calauan and Mabitac, two hot spots for bacterial blight disease in Laguna, Philippines. Different fingerprint patterns were detected from previously frozen, infected leaf samples analyzed by TCR using JEL1/JEL2 primers (Fig. 2). Since this method needs neither isolation nor cultivation of the pathogen, PCR of DNA from lesion exudates substantially reduces the time and resources required to fingerprint the bacterial blight pathogen, making it possible to conduct large-scale population studies in a cost-effective manner. ■

A method for estimating the number of eggs in egg masses of yellow stem borer

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Egg masses of yellow stem borer (YSB), *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker), are multilayered and densely covered with hair. Consequently, it is not possible to count the number of eggs in an egg mass, either before or after the eggs have hatched. This results in difficulties in many studies of YSB behavior and host plant resistance in which plants or plots are artificially infested with egg masses, and where interpretation of results would be more powerful if the number of larvae hatching from the egg mass was known. This study demonstrates the accuracy of a method of egg number estimation that we have developed, based on comparison of test egg masses with a "reference collection."

Our reference collection consists of 50 YSB egg masses of varying size, for which we have recorded the actual number of hatching larvae (range: 30-150 larvae). Based on dissection of many other YSB egg masses after egg hatching, we have found that, in a healthy egg mass, almost all eggs will hatch. Therefore, the number of eggs in an egg mass is generally equivalent to the number of hatching larvae.

We collected YSB adults from rice-fields in the vicinity of IRRI and caged them on rice plants in a greenhouse. We obtained 95 egg masses and visually compared each one with our reference collection. The egg masses were placed individually in vials and the number of emerging larvae was recorded.

Based on visual comparison with the reference collection, our mean estimate was 104.2 ± 2.6 ($n = 95$) egg masses, a number very close to the mean number of larvae that we later observed to emerge from these egg masses, 104.9 ± 2.8 . The relationship between the number of estimated and observed eggs per egg mass, $y = 0.87x + 13.3$,

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